

Polluter Pays Principle and its Application in India

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Upendra Vikram Singh

Research Scholar
Department Of Law
K.S. Saket P.G.College,
Ayodhya, Affiliated
Dr.RMLAU
Ayodhya,Uttar Pradesh,
India

Ashok Kumar Rai

Dean & Head
Faculty Of Law &
Department Of Law
Dr.RMLAU, Ayodhya, &
K.S. Saket P.G.College,
Ayodhya, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

Every living entity survives in a defined environment and industrialization is increasing very rapidly in the 21st century. Industries produce very harmful pollutants which are deteriorating our environment and having a direct impact on the existence of human and other living entity. Some of the principles applied to protect the environment are precautionary principle; polluter pays principle and absolute liability principle etc. This article explains what is the polluter pays principle? and its application in India and the role of the Indian judiciary in establishing the polluter pays principle in the field of environmental law.

Keywords Environment, Industrialization, Pollutants, Deteriorating, Polluter Pays Principle.

Introduction

The industrial revolution in the twenty-first century has brought significant improvement in people's lives. However, the Industrial Revolution has sadly led to industrial pollution. Technology has also advanced at an incremental rate, and manufactured goods have largely replaced obsolete goods. By-products are an essential component of manufacturing and it is the need of the hour that industrialists take measures to resolve the threats and hazards that these industries pose to our environment. Two principles have been applied to deal with this problem. (1)The "polluter pays principle" and (2) the "precautionary principle" are two important constitutional duties to prevent environmental degradation.

Aim of study

This article explains what is the polluter pays principle? and its application in India and the role of the Indian judiciary in establishing the polluter pays principle in the field of environmental law.

Review of Literature

The polluter pays principle (PPP) was first introduced by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in 1972 where the polluter was held responsible for pollution.[1]. In simple words PPP imposes liability on the person who pollutes the environment and compensates for the harm caused to human health or the environment in its original state. The polluter pays principle is one of the basic principles of environmental policy to guide sustainable development around the world. The main idea of the theory is that each polluter must achieve an economically efficient level of production and pollution and the polluter must look not only at the benefits of the polluting activity, but also at the harm it causes to others or the environment. In adopting the 'polluter pays' principle, the strategy was to make those who generate waste responsible for its recycling and disposal.

Although PPPs have helped reduce environmental damage to some extent, most developing countries have yet to sign on to it as a core environmental policy guideline. As beautiful as the idea behind the polluter pays principle may be, however, it has several theoretical and practical flaws to overcome (Ruhl and Craig, 2011). First, there remains ambiguity regarding clear identification of the actual polluter or who should bear the costs? Secondly, polluters may be poor households, informal sector companies, small and medium-sized companies in the formal sector and it is difficult to impose

liability on such polluters. All these issues make it difficult to implement PPP as a guideline for environmental policy in developing countries.

The "polluter pays" principle effectively holds polluters responsible for the environmental pollution they cause. According to this theory, the polluter should be held responsible for every environmental damage.[2] According to the "polluter pays principle", the polluter must pay for the rehabilitation of any environmental damage in addition to compensating the victims of pollution.

According to the OECD Recommendation (1) (2) of 1972 and 1974,[3]Public authorities decide what steps the polluter should take to manage the pollution so that the environment remains in a sustainable condition after the operation of such industry. As a result, both the cost of environmental restoration and the cost of health risks to the general public have to be borne by the polluter.

The polluter pays principle was most appropriately introduced in the case of Indian Council of Enviro-Legal Action v. Union of India in 1996.[4] In this case, Justice Dalveer Bhandari observed that the industrial process is integral to correcting the ecological imbalance it creates. Therefore, the polluting industry must bear the financial burden of taking preventive and control measures for pollution.[5] It is not possible to put the financial responsibility of avoiding or repairing this on the government. Because if the government has to compensate for the loss, ultimately the citizens will be demanded to compensate for the loss for which they are not guilty. After the court dismissed the writ petition, review petition and curative petition, several interim and interim applications were filed in the case. The judge in this case, Justice Dalveer Bhandari, observed that it is easy for people with power and authority to disobey or not follow judicial pronouncements.

As per the findings of the judges, in the cases of Vellore Citizen Welfare Forum v. Union of India and Ors[6] and Research Foundation for Science Technology National Resource Policy v. Union of India and Ors[7]. Respectively, environmental laws in India are fundamentally based on ethical principles such as the precautionary principle and the polluter pays principle. The "polluter pays principle" was previously considered a component of the accepted norms of international environmental law. Therefore, the judges believe that the concepts should be incorporated into Indian environmental rules.

In the case A.P. Pollution Control Board v. Prof. M.V. Naidu (Retd) and others.[8] The court has suggested that the parameters of how theory was put into practice were expanded. When cases are filed with tribunals or other environmental organizations, judges have made it possible for those institutions to adopt these principles.

Legal Provision

The fundamental rights of every Indian citizen have been emphasized through various articles of the Indian Constitution. The right to life and personal liberty is a fundamental freedom listed in Article 21.[9] Simply put, depriving the residents of an area of their basic rights would involve contaminating the area around them. It is the responsibility of every citizen to participate in the community to protect the environment as pollution is an inevitable byproduct of industrialization. Therefore, it is believed that Article 21 of the Indian Constitution naturally follows the right to community participation in environmental protection.

According to Section 20 of the National Green Tribunal Act,[10] while passing any order, award or decision for balanced development without harming Mother Earth, the Tribunal may apply the concepts of sustainable development; polluter pays principle and precautionary principle.

Roll of Judiciary-

Indian Council For Enviro-Legal Action V. Union of India and ORS.

A group of environmentalists spread awareness about the plight of people living in Bichhari, a Rajasthani village located in Udaipur district. In Bichari village, there was an industrial complex that mainly manufactured chemicals. The life of the villagers had become uncomfortable due to the release of concentrated sulfuric acid and aluminum sulphate from a company named Hindustan Agro Chemical Limited. Due to their refractory character, handling factory effluents was extremely challenging.

Some pollutants are leaching into the soil and polluting the aquifers and groundwater-below. The existing crop was also ruined due to dirty water. Wastewater seeped into the groundwater, making nearby water unfit for consumption and irrigation. As a result, it was decided that anyone who engages in an activity that involves the use of a chemical that is inherently dangerous is responsible for any harm it causes to people or the environment. The polluter pays principle is put into practice by holding the polluter financially responsible for all costs associated with restoring the environment to its pre-pollution state.

Vellore Citizens Welfare Forum V. Union of India and ORs

In the case Vellore Residents Welfare Forum v. Union of India and Others, residents of Tamil Nadu protested that untreated effluents from tanneries and other industries were dumped into waterways. Each day, the tanneries produced about 200 tons of leather; the production process requires 40 liters of water for every kilogram, and each liter of water contains 176 different types of dangerous acids. Potable water was contaminated as a result of the poisonous character of the waste materials. Rainfall and flooding in the surrounding city resulted in river water flowing into adjacent areas.

The surrounding fields were mainly used for agriculture and farming. As a result the agricultural sector became poisonous due to the effluents. The water became unfit for drinking or any daily use. As a result, in this case, the industrialists had to compensate for the losses incurred by them.

M.C. Mehta V. Union of India and Others

The "polluter pays principle" was reiterated by the Supreme court in this milestone case of M.C. Mehta v. Union of India and Others, [11] in which the Court emphasized on the absolute necessity of applying the principle.

In this case, there was cause for concern about the decline and fading of the Taj Mahal. The Taj Mahal is a monument of vital national importance; hence its maintenance is a matter of public importance. The National Institute of Environmental Engineering reports and the Varadarajan Committee reports of 1990 and 1995[12] respectively stated that most of the damage to the Taj Mahal was caused by the foundries, chemical industries and Mathura refineries, which were located in a designated area known as the Taj Trapezium Zone.

The court ordered that the industry either switch from gasoline to petrol or find a new place to operate. Industries disobeying the instructions were ordered to close without any justification. The "polluter pays principle" took on a new meaning thanks to Justice Kuldeep Singh in this landmark case. According to them, their employees will suffer losses as a result of closure or relocation of industries. The workers should have received compensation in the form of housing, continued employment until the industry revived, etc. Since then, the courts have repeatedly emphasized that the rights and obligations of workers cannot be violated. This incident marked a turning point in the administration of environmental law.

MC Mehta Vs. Union of India and ORS.

This case is also called the Oleum Case due to the nature of the waste generated from the industry.[13] The Court ruled that an enterprise engaged in a hazardous or inherently dangerous industry, which may endanger the health and safety of people working in the factory and people living in the surrounding areas, has a duty to the community which is complete and non-delegated. Ensure that no one is harmed as a result of the dangerous or inherently dangerous nature of the activity they undertake.

Notwithstanding any reasonable precautions taken by it, the enterprise is unquestionably bound to compensate for the loss. The amount of compensation payable for injury caused by accident in the conduct of a hazardous or environmentally hazardous activity carried on by the former industry.

Conclusion

It is important to note that one should not conclude that the polluter pays principle is a license for businesses to pollute. Industries cannot be started with dangerous goals knowing that you can pay for it later with money. Instead, it is a strategy to prevent environmental degradation. It is very important to save the environment and avoid destroying nature in the name of progress. There should be economic progress but not at the cost of the environment and vice versa. It is necessary to introduce legislation

incorporating such principles. We should work towards sustainable development without endangering our environment.

The National Green Tribunal should work prominently to strike terror into the hearts of industries and anyone found guilty of environmental pollution should face swift punishment. It is important to take the necessary action to guarantee that those who have been wronged receive adequate compensation. Last but not least, we should look at the polluter pay principle as a policy that will help us protect our environment, and not as a principle that is only concerned with compensation.

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